

LIQUID CRYSTAL THERMOSETS AS RESINS FOR HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES.

Mazhar Iqbal and Theo J. Dingemans*

Delft University of Technology

Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands

* corresponding author: E-mail: t.j.dingemans@tudelft.nl

SUMMARY

We are currently exploring a new family of wholly aromatic thermotropic liquid crystalline thermosetting polymers (LCTs) for structural aerospace composite applications. Liquid crystalline polymers offer excellent thermal ($T_g > 200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and mechanical properties, outstanding barrier characteristics and they can be processed into fiber-reinforced composites with superior mechanical and physical properties over PPS or PEEK-based composites.

Keywords: Liquid crystal polymer, thermosets, fiber-reinforced, composites.

INTRODUCTION

Thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers (TLCPs) have received considerable attention due to their attractive properties such as low melt viscosity, low coefficient of thermal expansion and excellent solvent resistance. These characteristics make them ideal candidates for high-performance fibers, coatings, fiber-reinforced composites and as packaging materials for electronic applications. However, despite their all-aromatic composition, main-chain TLCPs exhibit low glass transition temperatures ($T_g \sim 100 - 120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and low storage moduli at elevated temperatures, which significantly limits their final use temperature. Rigid rod-shaped polymers are intractable, insoluble and have melting temperatures above their decomposition temperature. Different structural modifications have been used in the past to suppress the melt transitions and to increase the processability of this class of polymers. Successful approaches include the copolymerization of several (non-linear) aromatic monomers to obtain random backbone composition, lateral substituents, flexible spacers in the backbone and reactive oligomer approaches.[1-5] In order to improve the processability we are utilizing our reactive LC oligomer approach, which allows us to take advantage of the low melt viscosity inherent to oligomeric species. In a successive, high temperature step, the reactive end-groups are activated and chain extension and crosslinking is initiated.

In this paper we will present our current work, where we have utilized the reactive oligomer approach towards the synthesis of melt processable all-aromatic ester-based TLCPs with T_g 's in excess of $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. We have modified a cheap LCP formulation based on Hydroquinone (HQ) and Terephthalic acid (TA), an LCP with a T_g of $267\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a T_m of approximately $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.[6] We have synthesized reactive

oligomers, based on TA and HQ, with a number average molecular weight (M_n) of 1000, 5000, and 9000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and varied the backbone composition using Isophthalic acid (IA), 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (HNA), 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid (HBA) or Chlorohydroquinone (Cl-HQ). We investigated the effect of molecular weight and backbone composition on the thermal and mechanical properties of these oligomers and their cured polymers. The use of these LCTs in the high-performance carbon fiber reinforced composites was also investigated.

SYNTHESIS OF THE PHENYLETHYNYL END-CAPPED OLIGOMERS

Our oligomers were synthesized using standard melt condensation techniques.[7-8] As an example, the synthesis of HBA/HQ/IA(32)-9K, the oligomer which we used for preparing carbon fiber reinforced composites, is shown in the Scheme 1. Yields of all oligomers were typically above 95%. The synthesis and experimental details are reported else where.[9]

Scheme 1. Synthesis of HBA/HQ/IA(32)-9K liquid crystalline oligomers with reactive phenylethynyl end-groups.

DYNAMIC THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to investigate the thermal stability and decomposition temperatures (T_d) of our fully cured LCTs. A heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ was used for these measurements. The thermal stability was evaluated in terms of 5% weight loss in both air and nitrogen (T_d). All LCT samples were cured at $370\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. in a nitrogen atmosphere and cooled to room temperature before each measurement. All LCTs showed excellent thermal stabilities ($T_d > 450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) both in air and nitrogen.[9]

POLARIZED OPTICAL MICROSCOPY

The phase behavior of our reactive oligomers, before and after crosslinking, was studied using polarizing optical microscopy. All reactive oligomers showed typical nematic textures and no nematic-to-isotropic (N-I) transition was observed. When these samples were cured at $370\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the viscosity of the melt increased and the samples

solidified after 1 h, exhibiting a fixed nematic texture. As a representative example, the nematic textures of a 5000 g.mol^{-1} TA/HQ/HNA(25)-5K, based oligomer, before and after cure, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Microphotographs of a 5000 g.mol^{-1} oligomer; TA/HQ/HNA(25)-5K, **A** low viscous nematic melt at $370 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, **B** Nematic thermoset after a 1 h. cure at $370 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. [9]

DYNAMIC MECHANICAL THERMAL ANALYSIS

The storage modulus (E') and glass transition temperatures were measured using DMTA in the temperature range of -100 to $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at 1Hz . Fully cured thermoset films exhibited high glass-transition temperatures and showed excellent moduli at elevated temperatures. With the reactive oligomer approach, we achieved a significant improvement in the glass transition temperature as compared to the commercially available LCPs such as VectraTM ($T_g = 110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) [5] and other well-known high performance polymers such as PPS. The storage moduli and T_g 's are summarized in Table 1 and a representative DMTA scan is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The storage modulus (E') of a fully cured TA/HQ/IA(50)-5K film. PPS is shown here for reference purposes (E' only). [9]

Table 1. Storage modulus (E') and T_g data of the fully cured nematic thermoset films

Sample	E' (GPa) at 25 °C	E' (GPa) at 100 °C	E' (GPa) at 150 °C	T_g (°C)
TA/CIHQ-5K	5.1	3.8	1.7	275
TA/HQ/IA(50)-5K	4.2	3.5	1.2	220
TA/HQ/HNA(25)-5K	3.9	2.6	0.68	186
TA/HQ/HBA(50)-5K	3.2	2.5	1.8	225
HBA/TA/BP(25)-5K	3.6	2.5	1.5	>200
HBA/TA/BP(25)-9K	2.1	1.5	1.0	>200
HBA/HQ/IA(32)-9K	3.9	3.2	0.07	184
PPS (Commercial)	2.9	-	-	94
Vectra (Commercial)	4.3	1.4	0.3	110

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NEAT RESINS

Injection molding techniques were used to obtain tensile and flexural specimens. The extruder was filled with polymer and heated to 350 °C to melt the precursor oligomer. The charge was held for 5 minutes at this temperature in order to obtain a uniform melt, after which pressure was applied to transfer the melt to the mold. The molding conditions are given in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Processing conditions for injection molding

Sample	Extruder Temperature (°C)	Mold Temperature (°C)	Injection Pressure (Bar)	Nozzle Diameter (mm)
TA/HQ/HNA(25)-5K	350	150	7.5	3

The temperature used to fill the mold was below the curing/crosslinking temperature of the oligomer. Most reactive oligomers synthesized by us can be processed as thermoplastics and have processing windows of 20-60 °C, during which no or very little chain extension or crosslinking takes place. Injection molded specimen were successively cured in a plaster of Paris mold.

The tensile and flexural properties of the injection molded test specimens are given in the Table 3. We observed that the low molecular weight oligomers have noticeably lower values for both tensile and flexural properties. When we cure these oligomers at 370 °C for 45 minutes we induce both chain extension and cross-linking and the mechanical properties improve significantly. These tensile tests were performed at a speed of 1mm. min⁻¹. The mechanical properties of the LCTs are summarised in Table 3. The results of PPS and Vectra LCP are included for reference purposes.

Table 3. Mechanical properties of the neat resins before and after cure.

Neat Resin Properties	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	% Elongation	T_g (°C)
TA/HQ/HNA(25)-5K (before cure) d=1.32	44	6.6	32	-	-
TA/HQ/HNA(25)-5K (after cure) d=1.32	110	7.9	66	5.5	186
HBA/HQ/IA(32)-9k	-	-	83	9.8	207
PPS (Commercial)* d=1.44	96	3.8	65	5	94
Vectra (Commercial) d=1.40	106	7.9	55	3	110

* Reference[10]

PROPERTIES OF THE CARBON FIBER-BASED COMPOSITES

In order to use these resins in fiber-reinforced composites, our HBA/HQ/IA(32)-9K resin was selected for further evaluation. T-300 Carbon fiber based composites (40 x 40 cm) could be made (60/40) and were analysed. From the preliminary results we concluded that this polymer shows similar, or in some cases, better properties in fiber reinforced composites as compared to well-known semi-crystalline polymers such as PEI (CETEX) and PPS. On average we found that the flexural modulus and tensile strength are comparable to PPS and CETEX-based composites, whereas the in-plane shear strength is significantly higher, i.e. 154 MPa as compared to 119 MPa for PPS and 118 MPa for CETEX-based composites. During these tests no delamination was observed, which suggests that LCT/CF-fiber shows better interfacial properties than PPS and CETEX-based composites.[11] The results are summarised in Table 5 and all values are an average of 5 measurements.

Table 5. Mechanical properties Carbon/LCT composites.

	Carbon/ LCT	Carbon/ PPS*	Carbon/ CETEX*
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	51	60	50
Tensile Strength (MPa)	671	758	656
In-Plane shear Strength (MPa)	154	119	118
In-Plane shear modulus (GPa)	3.2	4.04	3.3

* Data provided by TenCate.[11]

CONCLUSION

We have successfully synthesized all-aromatic liquid crystal thermosetting polymers (LCTs) with excellent thermal and mechanical properties. All fully cured polymers showed high glass-transition temperatures (184–275 °C), and exhibited high storage moduli at elevated temperatures (>1 GPa at 200 °C). All oligomers displayed nematic mesophases and in most cases, the nematic order was maintained after cure. Some oligomers exhibited low melt viscosities, which improved the processability towards fiber-reinforced composites. Carbon fiber composites prepared with these LCTs have a tensile strength of 671 MPa and in-plane shear strength of 154 MPa, which showed that these composites have similar or better fibers dominated properties but much better resin dominated properties in comparison to existing high-performance polymers. Based on these preliminary results, we believe that our polymers offer improved properties over current state-of-the-art high-performance polymers such as PPS, PEI and PEEK.

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